

**ON SOME GENERAL PROBLEMS OF LANGUAGE
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E-mail: akrom53@yahoo.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20695538>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 09th June 2026Accepted: 11th June 2026Online: 13th June 2026**KEYWORDS**

Language change, substratum, periods, monogenesis, polygenesis, language family, group of languages, speech, dialect, areal, historical principles, comparative-historical linguistics, Parent-language, pre-history

ABSTRACT

Concepts and ideas about the history of man's origin, growth, and future - as well as all of his divergent and convergent features—remain important since man is the paradigm's core object. It appears, that linguists have partly forgotten the history of languages under the current anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics, where pragmatics, cognitive linguistics, and linguoculturology are the main theme areas. However, this isn't actually the case.

Man has been studying language for two to three thousand years. Knowing that language is a perfect tool given to man, its nature always amazes man like a miracle, leaving an impression of an essence that is impossible to study to the end. Along with studying language, man also began to think about its history. Who created language? When was language created? Did the languages in the world develop from one language (monogenesis)? Or did languages initially develop from several languages (polygenesis)? Different people, such as kings, monks, scientists, poets or writers, gave different answers to such questions. Due to insufficient knowledge about language, the ideas expressed were very shallow, superficial and primitive, unable to shed light on the complex nature of language. The scientific study of the history of individual languages dates back to the formation of linguistics as a science in the 19th century and the initial results of comparative historical linguistics as a scientific method.

Representatives of the Indian and Greek schools of linguistics, as well as other ancient thinkers, mainly studied philological grammar, which, based on the models of Greek and Latin, was engaged in grammatically describing other, new written languages, developing normative grammars for their study, and compiling dictionaries. During this period, grammar was considered and studied not as a science, but as an art (*Ars grammatica*). Such grammars could not be included in the ranks of scientific grammars.

The fact that language is a changing historical category is accepted as a basic concept and principle only in the era of comparative-historical linguistics. This was a new approach to the study of language, which made it possible to give new, correct, truthful explanations to many things that could not be explained before, and to have a correct idea of the

development of language. This does not mean that the principle of historicity is observed only in comparative-historical linguistics. The scientific analysis of language in all existing schools and directions today cannot be carried out without the historical principle. The study of all units of language - phoneme, morpheme, word, phrase or sentence, taking into account the history of a particular language, is described in the science of history and with the help of this history. Even when it comes to a certain static state of the language, the application of this principle has remained a necessary condition for analysis. Now, in addition to the basic concepts of time, era, and history, the science of diachronic linguistics has also introduced the concepts of "history in a period," or history not related to "some" period.

The grammatical structure of languages remained outside the scope of comparative study. Such comparisons, which had no historical basis, did not contribute anything to the study of the true history of the language. What is important for linguistics is not any comparison, but a comparison based on history and carried out for the purpose of studying history. The cognitive value of a comparison that does not take into account history is minimal, if not extremely low. A comparison based on historically time-tested material becomes a powerful tool for studying history.

In conclusion, it can be said that the principle of historicity plays a very large, we can even say the main role in the formation of linguistics as a science. We cannot say that any research that refers to the history of language units and uses it for its own purposes is research conducted on the basis of the principle of historicity. Only research that is carried out systematically from consistent, clear historical facts to the interpretation of linguistic facts and serves to solve one or another problem existing in science can be called research based on the principle of historicity. The principle of historicity plays a very important role in the analysis of linguistic facts. However, despite this, misunderstanding of historicity, incorrect application or complete denial of it as a principle, lack of consistency in the application of the principle of historicity are frequent mistakes among linguists, so from time to time there is a need to protect this doctrine from various deviations and voluntarism. This happened twice in the history of linguistics. The first time was in 1950 during the critical analysis of the doctrine of N.Ya. Marr, and the second time was in 1957 in the famous discussion entitled "The Relationship between Synchronic Analysis and the Historical Study of Languages" and it was raised as the main issue on the agenda. In this discussion, very important issues were raised and their solutions were found. These issues were addressed many times in the subsequent stages of linguistics.

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